

Ni (II) Complex of 2-Mercapto quinazol-4-one

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2-Mercapto quinazol-4-one (HL) forms a green coloured chelate with Ni(II) which is found to be diamagnetic. Its analysis shows that it can be represented as ML_2 . It is assigned a square planar structure.

DAVE^{1,2} *et al.* studied the use of 2-mercapto 3-phenyl quinazol-4-one as a gravimetric reagent for copper. It was decided to similarly study its use for nickel. It was found that Ni(II) did not give any ppt. with this reagent at different pH. It was thought possible that the extra phenyl groups on position 3 were probably hindering compound formation through steric reasons. Hence the simpler reagent, 2-mercapto quinazol-4-one (HL), without the phenyl group on position 3 was prepared and its complex forming behaviour with Ni(II) was studied. Ni(II) readily forms a dark-green complex with HL.

Experimental

The yellowish-white reagent, 2-mercapto quinazol-4-one was prepared³ by refluxing thiourea with anthranilic acid at about 170°. The solid mixture, after the reaction was over, was extracted with 10% NaOH and reprecipitated by dil. HCl. The reagent was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 280°. The reagent was used as its 2% solution in alcohol. It was added to a dil. solution of nickel nitrate to which was added a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. A dark-green ppt. immediately forms. The pH at precipitation was maintained between 6 to 7. This ppt. was cooked, filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol. It was dried at 110°. It is insoluble in water. It was found to be soluble in alcohol and acetone. The ppt. is quite stable upto 150°. It is decomposed by acids and alkalis. In acids, the ligand is ppted while $Ni(OH)_2$ gets ppted. in alkaline medium.

The composition of the complex was determined by estimating nickel gravimetrically⁴ by means of dimethyl glyoxime (DMG). The results are given in Table 1.

The 1 : 2 composition of the complex was further confirmed by conductometric titration of an alcoholic solution of the reagent with an aqueous solution of nickel sulphate.

The molecular weight determined cryoscopically using camphor as a solvent, was found to be in the region of 400 to 418 showing that the complex was a monomer. The molar conductance, Λ_M , of the

TABLE 1.—2-MERCAPTO QUINAZOL-4-ONE CHELATE OF Ni(II).
(NiL_2)

Wt. of NiL_2 taken (gms)	Wt. of Ni (DMG) ₂ obtained (gms)	Wt. of Ni^{2+} found (gms)	Wt. of Ni^{2+} expected for NiL_2 on 1 : 2 basis
0.4000	0.2812	0.05716	0.05703
0.5000	0.3490	0.07094	0.07104
0.5020	0.3500	0.07115	0.07132

complex in alcohol solution was found to be about 9.0 mhos cm^2 per mole. This showed it to be a non-electrolyte.

Hence the complex can be represented as :

The chelating agent seems to behave as a bidentate ligand giving four-membered rings. The alternative ring formation through ketone on position 4 and NH on position 3 is considered less likely as sulphur, through back-donation, is likely to form a stronger complex than oxygen.

The room temperature magnetic susceptibility of the solid determined by the Gouy method is found to be $\chi_m^{corr} = -407 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units. Thus the complex is diamagnetic. The ligand, therefore, as expected for a thio-ligand, is fairly strong, forcing the last two electrons of Ni^{2+} into d_{z^2} orbital thereby pairing them off, indicating a square planar structure⁵ for the complex. The electronic distribution, hence, must be $(d_{xz})^2 (d_{yz})^2 (d_{xy})^2 (d_{z^2})^2$ giving a $^1A_{1g}$ ground

state for the complex. On this basis, three electronic $d-d$ transitions⁶ (i) $(d_z^2)^2 \rightarrow (d_z^2)^1 (d_{x^2-y^2})^1$, (ii) $(d_{xy})^2 \rightarrow (d_{xy})^1 (d_{x^2-y^2})^1$, (iii) $(d_{xz})^2$ or $(d_{yz})^2 \rightarrow (d_{xz})^1 (d_{x^2-y^2})^1$ can be expected. The electronic spectrum of the nickel chelate taken in solution in alcohol on Spectronic-20 actually shows three absorption bands in the visible region :

- i) $\nu_1 = 15870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 212$)
- ii) $\nu_2 = 17850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 267$) (shoulder)
- iii) $\nu_3 = 20000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 292$).

The general ligand absorption in this region seems to increase the intensities of the ligand field bands.

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